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**IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING THE STORAGE, TRANSPORTATION
AND SALE OF EXPORT-ORIENTED AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS**

**ВАЖНОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ХРАНЕНИЯ,
ПЕРЕВОЗКИ И ПРОДАЖИ ЭКСПОРТОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЙ
СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ**

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Abstract. Year by year the production of vegetables and fruits is growing in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. The quality of the vegetables and fruits also depends on their type and grade, on the other hand, the duration of their harvesting and disposal, and their elimination, the availability of commodities, embossing, transporting and storing. When done in a timely and well-mannered way, the quality and nutrition of the product will increase.

Particular attention is paid to the deep processing of agricultural raw materials and to the development of the storage of the stored crops. In 2015, the country has modernized and modernized 114 new agricultural refineries, 230 refineries and 77,000 800 tons of refrigeration cameras. Total storage capacity of fruits and vegetables in our country has reached 832 thousand tons. This will allow for a continuous increase in prices for seasonal seasonal supply of the population with major agricultural products, expanding exports of these products, and maintaining price stability.

Today, agricultural specialists have a great deal of practical knowledge of the technologies of cultivation, storage and processing of agricultural products. Getting acquainted with the quality of agricultural products, familiarizing with the standardization system, developing the technology of storing and processing agricultural products will improve the quality of products and minimize the damage. The current economic reforms will satisfy the needs of the population with high quality food products, one of the most pressing issues is radically equalizing the world standards.

Аннотация. В Республике Узбекистан из года в год растет производство овощей и фруктов. Качество овощей и фруктов зависит от их типа и класса, а также, — от продолжительности их сбора и транспортировки к потребителю. Цепочка от сбора до потребителя должна осуществляться быстро и качественно, т.к. это влияет на качество сельскохозяйственной продукции и показатель обеспеченности этим продуктом.

Особое внимание уделяется глубокой переработке сельскохозяйственного сырья и развитию хранения хранимых культур.

В 2015 году в стране были модернизированы и модернизированы 114 новых НПЗ, 230 перерабатывающих заводов и 77 000 800 тонн холодильных камер. Общая емкость фруктов и овощей в стране достигла 832 тыс тонн. Это позволяет постоянно увеличивать цены на

сезонные поставки населением основных сельскохозяйственных продуктов, расширять экспорт этих продуктов и поддерживать стабильность цен.

Сегодня специалисты сельского хозяйства владеют практическими знаниями о разных технологиях выращивания, хранения и переработки сельскохозяйственной продукции.

Зная качество сельскохозяйственной продукции, системы стандартизации, можно познакомиться с развитием сельскохозяйственного производства и технологии переработки в разных странах. Это, безусловно, повышает качество продукта и снижает возможные потери в сельском хозяйстве.

Экономические реформы республики направлены на удовлетворение потребностей населения высококачественными продуктами питания и одним из наиболее актуальных вопросов является радикальное выравнивание мировых стандартов.

Keywords: agriculture, logistics, management, food, Uzbekistan.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, логистика, управление, продукты питания, Узбекистан.

Introduction

One of the most important directions of foreign economic policy of each country during globalization of today's world economy is to further increase the country's export potential and to ensure its competitiveness on the world market. The export potential is not only a matter of a particular country, but also of the interests of each foreign economic activity.

It is well known that the country's prosperity, the further improvement of living conditions and human interests are the key elements of the ongoing economic reforms in our country. Agriculture plays an important role in our economy.

Year by year the production of vegetables and fruits is growing in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. The quality of the vegetables and fruits also depends on their type and grade, on the other hand, the duration of their harvesting and disposal, and their elimination, the availability of commodities, embossing, transporting and storing. It also increases the quality and nutrition of the product at the right time and at the same time. The high content of sugar, vitamins, biologically active substances and minerals that are essential for human organisms increases the nutritional, nutritional and medicinal significance of the flavor. So maintaining long-term storage of wet vegetables, fruits and grapes as high as possible is the main task.

As the whole world observes, the trends of agrarian sector such as fruits and vegetables, horticulture, viticulture and cattle breeding are rapidly developing. Last year, 12 million 592 thousand tons of vegetables and potatoes, 1 million 850 thousand tons of melons, 1 million 556 thousand tons of grapes and 2 million 731 thousand tons of fruits were grown.

On June 10, 2015 in Rome, the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) member countries were awarded awards for their efforts to end hunger. At this ceremony, Uzbekistan has become one of the 14 countries awarded for achieving the Millennium Development Goals in food security.

Over 7 million 500 thousand tons of grain and over 3 million 350 thousand tons of raw cotton were produced in Uzbekistan in 2015. In addition, the fruits and vegetables account for more than 18.7 million tons, of which 12 million 592 thousand tons are vegetables and potatoes, 1 million 850 thousand tons of melons and gourds and 1 million 556 thousand tons of grapes and 2 million 731 thousand tons of fruits (<http://www.pv.uz/uzk/node/69914>).

At the same time, according to the World Health Organization recommendation, in developing countries a daily allowance of 400 grams per person is 145 kg per year, in terms of consumption of fruit and vegetable products. The agricultural products grown in our country account for about 300 kg of vegetables per capita, 75 kg of potatoes and 44 kg of grapes. This indicator is three times as

optimally acceptable as the optimal consumption norm. It is well known that the potential of export of agricultural products in our country occupies one of the top places.

Literature review

Scientists from the agronomist economics S. N. Usmanov, R. H. Husanov, N. Hushmatov, T. Kh. Farmonov, A. Kodirov, Ch. Murodov, O. Jumaev, M. Sobirov, X. Xushvaqtova, Q. Hasanjonov, K. Choriev, A. Abduganiev, E. Akramov, A. Juraev, A. Shokirov, Sh. Kh. Muminov's scientific researches.

At the same time, the scientific works of these authors are devoted to the general economic issues in the development of fruit and vegetable industries at different times, and the development of the horticulture, fruits, storage and sales systems in the private sector are neglected.

Main part

Modern agricultural academicians have a good knowledge of the course of agricultural crop protection technology. Familiarity with the quality of agricultural products, familiarization with the standardization system, development of technology of storage and processing of agricultural products will improve the quality of products and minimize losses.

Human beings are engaged in the storage and processing of agricultural products since their consumption. It was one of the human needs that kept the product from storing and reducing its quality without any problems and quality. The nomadic tribes used natural warehouses for storing fruits and seeds - caves, puddles of trees, and later constructed private cellars. When the tribes began to live in tires, they started to learn to keep their surplus and protect them from pests.

Information on the storage and processing of agricultural products is reflected in Central Asia in the IX-XII centuries. Ibn al-Haytham (965-1035), Ibn Khatib al-Razi (1149-1209), Ibn Rashtah (XII century), Ibn Hammar (born 942) Muhammad ibn Bahram (died in 1194) Abu Hamid ibn Ali Ibn ' Hazrat Mashhadiy Sayid Muhammad (XVII century) refers to the processing of agricultural products. They have described in detail the benefits of these products and their need for the summer to be consumed.

Year by year the production of vegetables and fruits is growing in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. The quality of the vegetables and fruits also depends on their type and grade, on the other hand, the duration of their harvesting and disposal, and their elimination, the availability of commodities, embossing, transporting and storing. The quality and nutrition of the products will increase even more rapidly and in a timely manner [1].

Also, the high content of sugars, vitamins, biologically active substances and minerals that are essential to the human body increases the nutritional, nutritional and medicinal significance of the flavors. So maintaining long-term storage of wet vegetables, fruits and grapes as high as possible is the main task.

At the place where it is made — proven by the science and practice that farmers are eager to conserve fresh vegetables, fruits and grapes. Vegetables and fruits are kept in the farm, which is stored for a long time and declines by 15-20%. It should be noted that the achievements of science and advanced production in the field of vegetable and fruit fields, which have not yet been studied in terms of fruit and vegetable harvesting, transportation and storage in Uzbekistan, are still very small.

Hand made fruits and vegetables are expensive and do not meet the production requirements. Old storage methods have failed to meet the requirements of the current market economy. Therefore, it is necessary to look for and produce new methods that will keep good fruits and vegetables in good condition. For hot summer months in Uzbekistan, the regime of storage of these products, different types of warehouses, and methods of harvesting should be somewhat different [2].

It is well known that almost all vegetables are stored in a few hours to 8-9 months. However, only a fraction of the reduction in natural weight loss from the storage of new products will save tens of thousands of tons of products.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay serious attention to these issues in the fields of fruit and vegetable farms and procurement agencies and storehouses, so that the population can fully meet the requirements of fruit, grapes, potatoes, vegetables and melons. In order to provide the population with fruits and vegetables every year, each crop should be planned and planted on the basis of the approved plan.

It is worth noting that the state order for the purchase of fruits and vegetables, potatoes, melons and grapes from the 2016 harvest has been introduced. It's a good idea now and now, after a few more years, we will understand deeply.

As a result of consistent implementation of the complex measures on implementation of the most important tasks and priorities of the economic program for 2015, as well as consistent implementation of reforms in the economy and its sectors, reforming, structural transformation and diversification, sustainable growth rates in the first half of this year, macroeconomic stability and main macroeconomic indicators.

Compared to the first half of 2014, the gross domestic product grew by 8,1%, industrial output — by 8,1%, agriculture — by 6,5%. The further strengthening of macroeconomic stability was ensured by the surplus of the state budget surplus of 0,2% to GDP and USD 83,4 million of foreign trade turnover and gradual reduction of tax burden from 17.7% to GDP by 17,4% (<https://stat.uz/uz/>).

High economic growth rates have increased the total domestic incomes by 10,8 percent. Measures taken to stimulate consumer demand also reflected the increase in the volume of retail trade turnover by 14,8% and paid services to the population by 10,4%.

Within the implementation of the Program of development of the service industry for 2012—2016, the creation of more than 7.5 thousand service and service objects in the first half of this year allowed to increase the volume of services by 13,1% and increase the share of this sector to 52,9% in the GDP (2014 52,7 percent in the first half of the year).

Farmers who see so many experts in the agrarian sector acknowledge this decision as a timely document. There are two aspects to this. The first is related to the stage-by-stage reforms. That is, we had the opportunity to grow fruit and vegetable before, but we did not have enough storage facilities and processing facilities. We had little experience in the packaging of finished products [3].

Over the years, the tasks have been fulfilled on an evolutionary basis. To prove our point of view, it is enough to make a few numbers:

In 2015, there were created and modernized 114 new agricultural refineries, 230 new enterprises and 114 new cooling cameras with capacity of 77 thousand 800 tons. Total storage capacity of fruits and vegetables in our country has reached 832 thousand tons. This allows for uninterrupted supply of the population with basic agricultural products, while avoiding price increases during the year, with the exception of high-quality exports (<https://stat.uz/uz/>).

The second factor is the change in the world market of fruits and vegetables and melons. For example, the countries importing pomegranate or zucchini from other places are also coming to Uzbekistan at the same time. Because our products are characterized by the naturalness. Our country has won the trust of foreign partners in the field of cooperation. In our country the directions of agrarian sector such as fruits and vegetables, horticulture, viticulture and cattle breeding are developing at an accelerated pace. Last year, 12 million 592 thousand tons of vegetables and potatoes, 1 million 850 thousand tons of melons, 1 million 556 thousand tons of grapes and 2 million 731 thousand tons of fruits were grown.

By 2020, it is planned to create 304 large projects and 5,000 new production enterprises in the same sector only in the framework of state investment programs. This means that 100,000 tons of food products are produced annually. These projects pay particular attention to

the introduction of new technologies and deep processing of raw material, and most of them are in rural areas. The timely adoption of this resolution is based on the fact that the country's processing enterprises are regularly supplied with raw materials, and the domestic market is fully stockpiled with vegetables, potatoes, fruits and vegetables all year long, as well as fertile and competitive in foreign markets, a single system for their production, production, procurement, to increase the range and expand the range of exports of fruits and vegetables the testimony [8].

In particular, until January 1, 2019 enterprises of private ownership, processing fruit and vegetable, potatoes, melons and grapes, were exempt from customs duties (except for duties) on import of modern equipment and technologies irrespective of departmental affiliation. In the same period, the processing enterprises do not pay mandatory contributions to the State Targeted Funds, except for single social payment, income tax, property tax for legal entities, micro-firms and small businesses. Savings through tax and customs privileges help the entrepreneur to modernize production [2].

The main objective in the storage of fruits and vegetables is to preserve their physical and chemical properties, such as appearance, color, taste and nutritional value and other characteristics. Therefore, the right and scientific arrangement of the storage and processing of fruits and vegetables is in general the satisfaction of the population's demand for fruits and vegetables throughout the year.

In-depth study of the biological and physiological processes in the storage of fruits and vegetables and having a clear idea of this is essential in maintaining good quality products.

During the storage of good quality fruits and vegetables, it is important to know which processes will be affected and which factors influence the external environment.

Reduction of natural weight loss in the storage of fruits and vegetables will lead to an increase in production by only one percentage point. Therefore, experts should focus on the conservation of fruits and vegetables and must thoroughly investigate all the related issues.

Uzbekistan in the first quarter of 2016 increased the volume of exports of fruits and vegetables by 20%, and in January-March 2016 Uzbekistan increased the export of fruits and vegetables to 95.1 thousand tons. In order to further strengthen and develop the material and technical base for the storage of fruits and vegetables, 16 new refrigeration chambers for the storage of 10.5 thousand tons of fruits and vegetables were created, resulting in 53.1 thousand tons of vegetables (in the first quarter of 2015 110.6 percent) and 95.1 thousand tons of fruits and vegetables have been exported since the beginning of the year, "the report said [8].

Application of cutting-edge technologies in the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable production, introduction of modern methods of processing and storage of food products will help to prevent food shortages today. It is well-known that the production of fruit and vegetable products goes through a number of technological processes until the consumer reaches the finished product.

Not to prevent fruits and vegetables from just dying, but also to expand the cultivated area and to grow the gross harvest, also entails a great deal of expertise in this field. Priority should be paid to the selection of varieties and process of agrotechnical processing. Fruit and vegetable ripening results in good timing, timely harvesting and timely delivery to the next steps.

The main methods of producing fruits and vegetables to consumers are:

- delivery to new markets and supermarkets;
- storage;
- temporary storage warehouses;
- using special cooling cameras;
- Active frozen fruit and vegetable preservation.
- Recycling:
- drying of products;
- preparation of various canned products, juices, concentrates, jams, casserole and sour products [3].

The sequence of storage and processing of fruits and vegetables is as follows: Raw material base: Raw material base is one of the first factors for the establishment of agricultural products storage or processing enterprises. Because it is necessary to examine the raw material base of a storage warehouse or a processing company for the business plan and design of the business. During the study of the raw material base, the following is taken into account: the size and quality of fruits or vegetables planned to be stored or processed in the area. For example, if the regions specialize in vegetable growing, then it is necessary to establish or maintain vegetable-related storage or processing enterprises. The entrepreneur will examine the market demand for fruits or vegetables, or canned goods, and analyze the need for products and consumer needs [5].

Investigation of the infrastructure of the region includes:

- climatic conditions, location of the enterprise, land structure, wind direction, temperature and relative humidity;

- transportation system, enterprise's demand for transport, rail;

- power supply, its supply, long-distance power lines;

- availability of water supply, quantity of water, quality (hardness, softness), availability of water purification facilities. Labor force supply. This will explore the demand and supply of labor force in construction, and provide the company with qualified personnel. Selection and acquisition of technological equipment. The selection of technological equipment is mainly based on the fruits and vegetables stored or products planned for production. The following requirements apply when selecting the appliance:

- degree of mechanization (automation);

- energy saving;

- specialization - universalism, some productions; - Ease of use and safety;

- Effect on disposal and treatment of waste products and amount of waste. One of the other specific features of the selection of technological equipment is their complete system (line) or separately purchased. In such cases, experts believe that the equipment is technically a system, that is, purchasing a complete set. Cost structure of storage or processing enterprises. [4] There are a number of activities related to the use of funds for the storage or processing of fruits and vegetables, which differ greatly from other areas of agriculture. For example. If an entrepreneur purchases a certain type of tractor for processing a piece of land, then the cost after the acquisition of the equipment will be insignificant, ie the purchase of the tractor, and then the costs of its use will be spent on fuel and lubricants and various maintenance works. However, costs associated with the storage or processing of agricultural produce are the same. When designing cooling chambers and processing plants, it is crucial that the costs for organizing this sector be properly organized. Expenses for this can be divided into 2 groups (30-35% of the costs associated with the storage or processing of fruits and vegetables vary continuously 65-70%) (<https://mineconomy.uz/ru>).

Permanent costs include the area of cooling chambers, the building where the refrigeration chamber is built, all equipment for the operation of the cooling chamber, and associated costs typically include bank loans of various types and other annual payments;

Variable costs are those costs that can not be attributed to such costs, such as those identified by the market. These include, first of all, raw materials, labor costs, electricity, fuel and lubricants, various containers and auxiliary materials, transportation costs [6].

As it is well known, the population of our republic has great experience and long history in the storage of fruits and vegetables. Today, there are the following ways to store fruits and vegetables:

- natural storage: the products are stored in different cellars and pits, so no control over the storage process is possible, ie the products will depend on the ambient temperature and humidity;

- artificial storage: in artificial storage of agricultural products, the products are stored in specially designed buildings. Today, more than 80% of the conserved and consumed products in the world market share in artificially stored products. At the same time, the cooling chambers in the

buildings will be created and maintained in such a way as to ensure the proper appearance of fruits and vegetables with special equipment [6].

Technology of storage of fruits and vegetables

The main purpose of storage of winter products is to preserve and convey the beneficial ingredients of the raw material for all human organisms collected until the ripening of the raw material. During the storage of fruits and vegetables, there are several major causes of the loss of useful nutrients contained in them, such as:

- Reduction of quality of raw materials and disappearance of substances:
- factors affecting the conditions of cultivation and agro-processing, methods and conditions of harvesting, changes in their structure under the influence of various diseases (microorganisms, parasites), raw materials by various animals;
- Reduced quality of fruit and vegetables as a result of respiration and loss of moisture.

Today, with the advancement of science and technology, several modern technologies for maximizing the quality of fruits and vegetables are created and put into practice. The key features of this approach are:

- Fruit and Vegetable Loss Factors:
- Reducing the temperature of the storage chamber;
- Optimization of relative humidity in the cooling chamber;
- change the air content in the cooling chamber.

The process of harvesting and storage of fruits and vegetables can be understood as follows. During fertilization, they breathe carbon dioxide gas and collect the necessary ingredients as a result of the photosynthesis process.

When the fruits and vegetables are harvested, this process begins when the oxygen absorbs air, carbon dioxide gas, separation of moisture, and a certain amount of heat dissipation. These processes, which are part of the fruit and vegetable, are called metabolism or aging. The main purpose of agricultural storage and processing specialists is to protect the beneficial ingredients in raw materials by preventing the above-mentioned metabolic processes. For each fruit or vegetable stored in the warehouses, it is necessary to approach them based on their chemical composition.

It should be noted that, in addition to the different temperatures of fruits or vegetables, it is not recommended to store them in a single cell. The reason for this is that when storing the gas, gas is emitted (called gas ethylene gases), which can be second-frozen to gas separated from one fruit, resulting in reduced storage life.

Nowadays, demand for buyers is largely dependable on fruits and vegetables of high quality and appearance, and the greater degree of awareness and adaptation of the system of producers, savings and sales of these changes is the main source of income growth.

Due to the fact that the system of storage and transportation of damaged gardening products is not well established, the damage is a huge loss not only for the farmer, but also for the country's economy. Specifically:

- Due to the different disproportions in the storage and transportation of gardening products, the damage to the agricultural sector is primarily due to the loss of horticultural products. According to estimates, the loss of fruits and vegetables in the country (loss of non-consumers after ripening) reaches 30-35%. This will result in the loss of direct financial impact on the farmer;

- low productivity due to low productivity of the storage system. As a result, the farmer will lose average 20-25% of real income due to the decline in product quality (the average market price drops). The lost funds will make it possible to invest in the development of private farming. Also, this affects the development of other branches of the economy, which are related to horticulture; (www.xs.uz, <http://www.pv.uz/uzk/node/69914>).

- Due to the lack of system of storage and sale of products, losses of the production and service sectors, as well as the loss of profits due to the loss of the product, have a negative impact on the development of the social sphere. These negative impacts are characterized by a decrease in revenues from production, processing, services, and a decline in social development;

- Inadequate development of storage and transportation systems leads to the quality of products offered to the consumer, chemical composition violation and sanitation. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the health of consumers. The means to restore human health are damaged by the fact that those who engage in the work are not exposed to work, and that the labor productivity is reduced to the society, which can not be easily understood. Therefore, savings for the development of the storage system and the reductions in reforms in this area are economically justifiable.

At the microeconomic level, the farmers and service providers will have the opportunity to generate significant social and economic benefits to the society at the macroeconomic level through the development of the field of storage, the creation of modern warehouses, the widespread use of modern techniques and technologies in their equipment, .

The main factor in raising product competitiveness is the introduction of seasonal storage in warehouses, creation of necessary storage conditions, control over the quality of products, compliance with storage rules, their selection, packing and shipping.

The development of horticultural products storage is recommended in three main areas:

- establishment of private or cooperative forms of gardening by private farms;
- Establishment of funds and fixed assets of agro-firms within the framework of fruit and vegetable agro-industrial companies;

- Agricultural products can be organized at the wholesale markets, on the basis of investments and markets of wholesale markets.

When organizing the product storage it is necessary to single-handedly pick up the container. In this case:

- By qualitative and quantitative measurements, wholesale and retail buyers save time for their quality and quantity;

- Installation of products from the warehouse or at the wholesale sale of the goods at the same time with the installation of their own containers in vehicles will require less expenses, preventing the quality of the product;

- It is possible to increase the level of mechanization of loading, upgrading and discharging of large warehouses.

It is desirable to develop the following areas of expansion of the gardening products storage system in the long term:

- Establishment of large-scale warehouses for fruiting the airflow in the building, controlled by artificial cooling, temperature and humidity;

- Establishment of warehouses for controlling the quality of products in polyethylene masks in frozen food;

- construction of a small air storage system, allowing the storage of temperature and humidity in the naturally occurring small and rapidly degrading fruits.

Fruit is imported into the domestic market, while most of the fruits are consumed in the market without falling into the market. Therefore, in developing the horticulture industry, there is a need to improve the sales system. This necessity is primarily due to the fact that the sales sector is the final stage in the production and consumption of goods. Because, during the preparation, storage, selection, packaging and sale of the product, consumer value is created, its appearance improves and its marketability increases.

Nowadays, getting the attention of consumers and farmers who sell their products to the market is the result of additional services.

Given the high demand in the market for high quality and beautiful goods, it can be said that domestic and foreign markets are largely dependent on the quality and appearance of agricultural products. It is important to ensure that products are sorted, packed, packaged and supplied in a timely manner to the consumer.

Figure. Development trends in horticultural products

In wholesale markets, the organization of sorting, packaging and packing of products is carried out by: firstly, by the quality and size of fruits and vegetables, which allows consumers to buy satisfying products in terms of quality and size, and thus one of the most important factors in business - time savings;

Secondly, transporting fruits and vegetables in bottles, loaded with bottles, requires less cost and time than loading them onto the ladder, as well as little labor;

Thirdly, qualified specialists, who master the specifications of each product, the rules of loading, transportation in the wholesale market, will provide service and consulting services to their buyers.

Fruit and vegetables can be damaged if they are transported to the luggage, which can be damaged or lost in the course of transportation, and the wholesale buyer can be seriously damaged. The full introduction of the aforementioned types of services in the wholesale market of agricultural products will have a great economic effect and in the end the economic mechanism of the market will be formed, thereby creating favorable conditions for producers and sellers.

The horticultural storage system, which is organized in various forms and forms of ownership, should also include the process of sorting, packaging and packaging of products that are complex. Because these processes related to the storage of goods can be performed separately, in practice they are interconnected and one requires the other. In particular, it is desirable to select the storage items to be mechanically exposed from the outside, the size, the size, the degree of ripeness.

The selection of the most frequently damaged gardening products will be done by placing them in special containers. It is desirable to arrange quality and consumption examination simultaneously at the dishes.

It is important to determine the level of compliance of the consumption control with the requirements of existing standards before the selection of the damaged gardening products.

Prior to the storage of horticultural products that have been violated quickly, certain rules and regulations must be observed. These rules should, in addition to common law, require the maximum consideration of market demand, first of all, with the manufacturer's objectives. Therefore, in the selection of products, it is desirable to take into account the following key indicators of the product, directly affecting the market price of the product and the formation of the consumer demand:

- appearance, color, ripeness, complications of mechanical effects on the outer appearance of the garden products; It is important to pay attention to the fact that the size of the garden products is the same. Observations show that the product range depends on the fact that in most cases the size of the fruit and vegetable products is not the same as the size of the product;

- The issue of chemical composition and suitability of the product is also very important. However, the complexity of this issue is that the chemical composition of the product is an abnormal indicator for the consumer in the market, in which it is desirable to add the quality certificates issued by the relevant laboratory in accordance with the legislation;

- The taste, odor, appearance and the like of other gardening products should also be taken into account.

With the help of seasonal gardening, the marketplace will be able to stabilize prices. Also, the opportunity to invest in the development of production in a wide range of industries will increase considerably thanks to the benefits generated through sales of products at higher prices.

Large dimensions of the products storage system are determined by regional conditions, production volumes, proximity of production to market. Accordingly, there is also a difference in the complexity of equipment depot and installation of the cooling system. Specifically, smaller warehouses may have a lower quality and complexity if they allow large storage facilities to be equipped with a complex cooling system and quality control equipment (economically cost-consuming).

During the storage of products, one-way sorting and bottlenecks are a great deal of convenience. Including:

- By qualitative and quantitative analysis of the products, wholesale and retail buyers will be able to save their purchased goods and save a lot of time on quality and quantity of their products;

- Installation of products from the warehouse or, at the same time, the loading of the container to the vehicles at the same time requires less expenses, preventing product quality deterioration in

these products;

- It is possible to increase the level of mechanization of loading, sorting, lifting and dismantling of warehouses in large sizes.

Conclusion

It is desirable to develop the following areas of expansion of the storage of horticultural products in the long term:

- Construction of large storage facilities, controlled by airflow in the building, controlled by artificial cooling, temperature and humidity;

- Establishment of warehouses that allow to control the quality of products by using polyethylene masks in a gaseous fruit and vegetable environment that allows for longer storage;

- It is also necessary to store small quantities of products and to build a controlled, air-conditioned (ventilated) small storage facility that allows the storage of temperature and humidity in the naturally occurring (for example, apple, pomegranate, pear, etc.).

Fruit weight decreases when storing gardening products. This reduction also depends largely on the storage conditions and methods, the specific characteristics of the fruits stored, storage life, and other conditions. In particular, the loss of crops due to a significant change in the biochemical composition of crops (crop defects) constitutes 0,3-0,5% of the product deposited at storage of winter varieties, while the natural decrease in this period reaches 2,0-2,4%. During the five months of storage, the decrease in product degradation will be 3,0-3,5% and the natural decrease will be 3,5-5,0% (www.xs.uz, <http://www.pv.uz/uzk/node/69914>).

The controlled storage of the products in the controlled environment plays an important role in preventing the reduction of the product. In order to use this method it is necessary to master necessary technologies and to train specialists.

In general, a large-scale socioeconomic development of the farmers and service providers at the microeconomic level, at the macroeconomic level, and the socioeconomic status of the society through the development of the gardening products storage, the creation of modern warehouses, the widespread use of modern techniques and technologies in their equipment, economic benefits.

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